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THE AESTHETICS OF ETERNAL PARADOX: ENDLESS DIALOGUE BETWEEN ISLAMIC AND MINANGKABAU THOUGHT IN WISRAN HADI'S DRAMATURGY

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Abstract: *Wisran Hadi, a prominent Indonesian playwright, was born in the cultural background of the Minangkabau ethnic group, one of the ethnic groups in Indonesia that have received the most attention from world researchers. There are two main reasons, which make this ethnicity get special attention in humanities studies. First, because the Minangkabau ethnic contributed many thinkers during the formation of the Indonesian nation-state, which is believed to have originated from its egalitarian and democratic culture; and secondly because the matrilineal system in its customs is strongly intertwined with Islam which tends to be patriarchal. In this endless paradox, many literary writers are born. Wisran Hadi was one of them and became the most prolific and strongest of his time. In his drama works, Wisran Hadi makes the eternal paradox between Islam and Minangkabau a dialogical force, from which aesthetic value emerges as the ability to negotiate and make appropriations. When staged, the dialogue between the two sources of paradox is presented in the form of visual games, which gives the impression that differences of mind for the Minangkabau ethnic are understood as a game of life, a source of wisdom, and even a philosophy of life that is useful for shaping humans and their humanity. This paper is intended to show that in the form of typical dramaturgical architecture, this endless paradox becomes the aesthetic experience that Wisran Hadi offers to his audience through his drama works.*

Keywords: *aesthetics, paradox, Islam, Minangkabau, Wisran Hadi, dramaturgy*

Introduction

Wisran Hadi (1945-2011), is one of the leading playwrights in Indonesia. He is even considered one of the most dominant writers on the literary map in Indonesia in the era of 1980 to 2000.¹ This is understandable, considering that Wisran Hadi is a 15-time winner of the

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¹ Lastry Monika, "Posisi Dan Pencapaian Wisran Hadi Dalam Arena Sastra Indonesia (Position and Achievements of Wisran Hadi in the Indonesian Literature Arena)," *Medan Makna: Jurnal Ilmu Kebahasaan Dan Kesastraan* 19, no. 2 (2021): 137, <https://doi.org/10.26499/mm.v19i2.3513>.

Drama Writing Competition, the Jakarta Arts Council, one of the most prestigious events in drama text writing in Indonesia. He was awarded the Best Indonesian Writer (1991, 2000), South East Asia Write Award (2000), Republic of Indonesia Art Award (2003), Exemplary Writer and Cultural Award (1976, 2005), and the Indonesian Theater Federation Award (2010). Until now, the drama script he wrote is one of the most widely performed drama scripts by Indonesian writers, especially by campus theaters.

Because of his position, Wisran Hadi also received a lot of attention in the world of literary studies. The study of his work spans aspects of intertextuality, sociology, elements of cultural anthropology, linguistic elements, to historical elements. Wisran Hadi is seen as one of the playwrights with the intertextuality method, two where the primary approach he uses is demystification.² With intertextuality, Wisran Hadi reworked various texts into drama texts, including literary texts and Minangkabau oral traditions, as well as historical texts. In this way, he indirectly demystifies, that is, strips away the mythical nature of various texts to make them more useful as lessons for today's audience and readers.

Unfortunately, not many articles have been written about dramaturgy and the aesthetic concept behind Wisran Hadi's drama works. Considering that fact, this article is an attempt to examine Wisran Hadi as *homo narans*, creatures who communicate through stories, in this case in the form of drama, as a way to build their socio-cultural world and, at the same time, create meaning of that world. Departing from this concept, Wisran Hadi can be seen as an example of *homo narans par excellence*, who cannot only tell his views on life in the form of drama, but also can create an 'enchanted' style in his texts. the drama script, even in its performance. The primary fascination technique in the drama texts is rhetoric, namely puns, which shows the height of language and the superiority of culture. Meanwhile, when staged, the drama works manifest in the form of 'visual games,'³ which a prominent Indonesian dramaturg and scenographer, Roedjito, calls "painting on the stage."⁴

This, the relationship between form and content of a play, and a way of putting the two together as a coherent structure, is understood in the

² Umar Junus, *Mitos Dan Komunikasi* (Jakarta: Sinar Harapan, 1981).

³ Sahrul Nazar, "Pamenan as an Aesthetic Concept of Creating a Wayang Padang Theatre," *Dance & Theatre Review* 1, no. 1 (2018): 22–35, <https://doi.org/10.24821/dtr.vii1.2248>.

⁴ Dede Pramayoza, *Melukis Di Atas Pentas: Selisik Penyutradaraan Teater Wisran Hadi* (Yogyakarta: Penerbit Deepublish, 2020).

aesthetic experience of drama and theatre as dramaturgy.⁵ Furthermore, the discussion about dramaturgy contains two things at once, namely the internal structure of the play text, as well as the composition of various external components in the performance, including the concept of staging, its political value, and a study of the audience who is the target of the play text.⁶ Thus, a play text in the theater is understood as an aesthetic entity and as a vehicle for ideology. Based on this understanding, in this article, we will express various debates of thought through characters in the play text of Wisran Hadi, which is believed to harbor a distinctive view of Wisran Hadi, or – borrowing the term of Synne K. Behrndt – typical dramaturgical thinking of Wisran Hadi.⁷

Dramaturgical Material: Islamic Shari'a and Minangkabau Customs

Wisran Hadi's cultural views, reflected in the drama scripts he wrote and subsequently became the primary material for his dramaturgy, cannot be separated from his socio-cultural background and personal history of life. Wisran Hadi was born as the son of a scholar. His father, Haji Darwis Idris (HaDI), from whom he got the surname Hadi, was a commentator and was the high priest at the Muhammadiyah Mosque in Padang City, West Sumatra. Wisran Hadi himself was initially directed by his father to take an education that could lead him to become a religious teacher. Following his father's advice, Wisran Hadi completed his high school education at PGA (Religious Teacher Education).

But then his life took a turn when he finally decided to continue his education at ASRI (Indonesian Fine Arts Academy) in Yogyakarta. At this art college, he met many people who later became his partners and rivals in the theater world in Indonesia. One of them is Putu Wijaya. Returning to West Sumatra after completing his studies at ASRI, Wisran Hadi taught at the SMSR (Secondary School of Fine Arts) in Padang. In this place, the seeds of his love for the world of art at large and finally for theater and drama began to grow. In his journey, the values of liberal arts and modernity, and Islamic values started to dialogue in his mind, which was reflected in his works.

The dialogue is complete when he later becomes the husband of Puti Reno Raudah Thaib, who is Puti (Princess) from Linduang Bulan Palace,

⁵ Cathy Turner and Synne K Behrndt, *Dramaturgy and Performance* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2008), 25.

⁶ Mary Luckhurst, *Dramaturgy: A Revolution In Theatre* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2005), 10-11.

⁷ Synne K. Behrndt, "Dance, Dramaturgy and Dramaturgical Thinking," *Contemporary Theatre Review* 20, no. 2 (2010): 185–96, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10486801003682393>.

Pagaruyung, in Tanah Datar Regency. Linduang Bulan Palace itself is seen as a symbol of the inheritors of Minangkabau customs. Although juridically-formally, people understand that the heirs of the Linduang Bulan Palace, Pagaruyung, are not rulers both administratively and culturally, various values and cultural heritage of Minangkabau customs are believed to be well preserved because of the participation of the Linduang Bulan Palace family, Pagaruyung as heir and final guardian.

These two family bases, which were united by marriage between Wisran Hadi and Puti Reno Raudha Thaib, later became a factor that cannot be underestimated in viewing Wisran Hadi's creative process. Through the union, Wisran Hadi had access to explore various intricacies of the family and the rules in the Pagaruyung kingdom, which is one of the crucial references for understanding Minangkabau customs broadly. Meanwhile, from his father's education and his formal education, Wisran Hadi also has sufficient insight to understand Islam and its complicated relationship with Minangkabau customs. Finally, we can say that one of the cultural capitals of Wisran Hadi is his position as: "Son of a *Buya*, Husband of a *Puti*," as also expressed by other writers.⁸

Wisran Hadi was not only born and raised but also spent his age and even breathed his last in Padang, West Sumatra, one of the provinces on the island of Sumatra, Indonesia. West Sumatra is a province with a majority ethnic Minangkabau population. West Sumatra attracts the attention of many foreign researchers, who are often referred to as Indonesianists because of some of their uniqueness. The main factor is that this ethnic group gave birth to many intellectuals during the struggle for Indonesian independence. In contrast, other ethnic groups besides Javanese did not produce many scholars, and therefore played an essential role in the fight for independence. In addition, the Minangkabau ethnic group applies matrilineal culture in its customs and at the same time, paradoxically applies *syara'* or Islamic religious teachings that tend to be patrilineal.⁹

Realizing that he lives in an ethnic society with a distinctive character, Wisran Hadi builds his artistic tradition by combining the richness of traditional literature and oral traditions with modern literary and drama

⁸ Dedi Arsa, "Representasi Atas Padri & Suara-Suara Muslim Moderat: Telaah Atas Empat Naskah Sandiwara (Representation of The Padri & Moderate Muslim Voices : A Study of Four Plays)," *Jentera: Jurnal Kajian Sastra* 10, no. 1 (2021): 73–93, <https://doi.org/10.26499/jentera.v10i1.2613>.

⁹ Jeffrey Hadler, *Sengketa Tiada Putus: Matriarkat, Reformisme Agama, Dan Kolonialisme Di Minangkabau* (Jakarta: Freedom Institute, 2010); Tsuyoshi Kato, *Adat Minangkabau Dan Merantau; Dalam Perspektif Sejarah.*, ed. Terj., Gusti Asnan, and Akiko Iwata (Jakarta: Balai Pustaka, 2005).

tools so that his works can be viewed as hybrid works created by eclectic method.¹⁰ He said such things himself when he exposed the concept of dramaturgy. For Wisran Hadi, a theater tradition must be built on awareness of the audience, history, and theater traditions in the area concerned. Departing from that, he straightforwardly said that the form of theater he developed was a combination of the conditions in the *randai* (Traditional Minangkabau Theatre) with modern theater meanwhile traditional Minangkabau stories (commonly referred to as *Kaba*), he added elements of logic into it.¹¹ The spectator community, who has the *randai* and *kaba*, is none other than the Minangkabau ethnic community, who simultaneously apply their customary matrilineal system, with patriarchal Islamic teachings.¹²

Upon closer inspection, the differences between these two value systems become even more apparent. The first thing is about the source of knowledge. Minangkabau adat tends to apply materialism and empiricism, which can be seen in several adages in adat. The most famous phrase and the title of the book written by A. A Navis, one of the leading Minangkabau culturalists, is studying nature, mentioned in the adage: “*Alam takambang jadi guru*” (nature expands make as a teacher).

In the adage, it is clear that for the Minangkabau people, the main source of truth that guides their life is the laws of nature, which of course have materialism and empiricism at the same time. Various value systems in Minangkabau customs are sourced from learning about the natural surroundings. For example, the Minangkabau people accept various changes in their lives because they believe that every era will bring about change. This is also reflected in their traditional adage which says: “*Sakali ayia gadang sekali tapian berubah*” (once a great stream, once the edges move).

While on the other hand, it is easily understood that Islamic Sharia, or in the language of the Minangkabau community is *Syara'* which tends to apply idealism, where the only source of truth is the Quran and Hadith. Although Islam also recognizes the existence of *Ijtima* or the decisions of the scholars, which can be taken through dialogue, basically the tendency of idealism or holding fast to lessons that come down from the sky is the main thing in taking knowledge and truth in Islam.

¹⁰ Pramayoza, *Melukis Di Atas Pentas: Selisik Penyutradaraan Teater Wisran Hadi*.

¹¹ Wisran Hadi, “Sebuah Konsep Kerja Teater: Dari Apa Yang Telah Ada,” in *Pertemuan Teater 80*, ed. Wahyu Sihombing, Slamet Sukirnantono, and Ikraneegara (Jakarta: Dewan Kesenian Jakarta, 1980), 125–29.

¹² Sidik Tono et al., “The Harmonious Relationship between Minangkabau Custom and Islam in the Distribution of Inheritance,” *Al-Shajarah* 2019, no. Special Issue Sharia and Law (2019): 39–55.

The logical consequence of these two ways of thinking will also show the contrasting differences between the two in terms of seeing the human position. Departing from its materialism, Minangkabau customs say that all people stand equal before history, which is reflected in their proverbs: “*Duduk samo randah tagak samo tinggi*” (Sit the same low, stand the same height), which means that all humans can stand on equal footing, equally and with the same taste. Meanwhile, Islam, although it does not introduce a hierarchical system, basically puts humans in a hierarchy based on, at least, their closeness to the Highest Essence, namely the Great Creator, Allah.

The egalitarian nature of Minangkabau customs then encourages a government system that tends to be more democratic, which is directly proportional to the hierarchical nature taught by Islam, which then gives birth to a government that tends to be autocratic. This is also reflected in the implementation of legislation and government of the *Nagari* system, in which the *Wali Nagari* is democratically elected by the entire *Nagari* community, and between one *Nagari* and another are standing parallel, and can form a system known as *Luhak*, which is a form of a federation of *Nagari*. That their union is mainly on defense and security alone, while the day-to-day running of the *nagari* is left to the style and agreement of each. This is of course different from how Islam teaches about the caliphate, where there is a leader who is the center of the state leadership called the caliph, which is later misinterpreted as a form of the sultanate in history of Islamic civilization.

Based on this, it is very clear that between Minangkabau customs and Islamic law there are so many differences based on the epistemology of each of these philosophical systems. While Minangkabau’s traditional philosophy comes from learning about nature which is very materialistic, philosophy in Islam comes from teachings sourced from the Qur’an and Hadith, which are idealistic. Therefore, it is pretty natural that researchers have seen the Minangkabau people live in various dichotomies and ‘eternal paradoxes’ throughout its history.

Why not, the main paradigm used in the process of self-identification and the world by the Minangkabau people is the *adat* (customs) that they imagine persisting, across generations, as expressed in the adage: “*Adat nan indak lakang dek paneh, indak lapuak dek hujan.*” (A custom that doesn’t fade because of the heat, doesn’t rot because of the rain). However, in practice today, Minangkabau *adat* is interpreted as a result of synthesis with and *syara’* (Islamic teachings). It is understood as inseparable from one another, as seen in the discourse. “*Adat Basandi Syara’, Syara’*

Basandi Kitabullah” (Customs based on Islamic teachings, Islamic teachings based on the Qur’an).¹³

The main source and at the same time, the main medium of the endless encounter and dialogue between these two value systems is the Padri War (1803-1838), which started as a ‘civil war’ between the adat and the clergy, known as the Padri, and later turned into an anti-colonial war when the two camps united to fight Dutch. Dutch colonial researchers themselves saw that social jealousy was the trigger for this conflict, in which the *Ulama* (religious leader), who were also teachers, slowly became an important social class in Minangkabau society, competing with the *Penghulu* (traditional leader). The latter were culturally an important social class before. Meanwhile, contemporary researchers from outside tend to see that economic factors, in which there is a conflict of interest between 3 parties, namely the Padri, the *Penghulu*, and the Colonial, are the driving factors for this war.¹⁴

Despite these various versions, the Padri war was the beginning of a central paradox in the life of the Minangkabau people, which one expert later called an ‘endless dispute.’ The peace between the adat community and the religious community confirms (again) what is known as the “Bukik Marapalam Charter,” which is an agreement to carry out both customs and Islam simultaneously. Both, as has been shown, contain contradictory ideas. The result is an ambivalence towards the two paths of their cultural heritage, which is summarized in a formula that is seen as a golden rule, namely the Bukik Marapalam Charter, in which adat and religious people make a peace agreement, which is then enshrined in the statement: “*Adat Basandi Syara’, Syara’ Basandi Kitabullah*” (Customs based on Islamic teachings, Islamic teachings based on the Qur’an).

As a further result, the researchers saw that psychologically the Minangkabau people seemed to be plagued by the masochism syndrome, namely feeling pleasure by hurting themselves. The reason is that there are not many ethnic groups that are ambivalent and masochistic like this towards their ethnic group or hometown.¹⁵ This ambivalent attitude has an impact on various sectors of their lives. Migrants, for example, who are

¹³ Dede Pramayoza, *Dramaturgi Sandiwara: Potret Teater Populer Dalam Masyarakat Poskolonial* (Yogyakarta: Penerbit Ombak, 2013), 60-61.

¹⁴ Christine Dobbin, *Gejolak Ekonomi Kebangkitan Islam Dan Gerakan Padri: Minangkabau 1784-1847 (Islamic Revivalism in a Changing Peasant Economy, Central Sumatra 1784-1847)* (Jakarta: Komunitas Bambu, 2008).

¹⁵ Rika Valentina Tengku and Roni Ekha Putera, “Posisi Perempuan Etnis Minangkabau Dalam Dunia Patriarki Di Sumatera Barat Dalam Perspektif Agama, Keluarga Dan Budaya (The Position of Ethnic Minangkabau Women in the Patriarchal World in West Sumatra in the Perspective of Religion, Family and Culture),” *Demokrasi* VI, no. 2 (2007): 1-19.

seen as one of the good consequences of matrilineal culture in Minangkabau, want to bring new things to their hometown, but at the same time, like the adat in the village to persist.¹⁶

Dramaturgical Architecture: The *Padri* and The *Penghulu* in Drama

Aesthetic concept behind a drama work can be understood through the architecture of the drama itself, namely the characters, plots, and themes that are raised and stored behind the genre and style of the drama work itself. When dealing with a drama text, one is faced with several elements that build drama, which can be used to investigate further the views and concepts promoted by the playwright. Based on that theory, Wisran Hadi's drama scripts can also be used to review dramaturgy and, finally its aesthetic vision, taking into account the characters, plots, and themes of the drama scripts he wrote.

Wisran Hadi chose four characters in the history of the Padri war, each of which he put in a text as the main character or central character. He described four Padri figures in four play scripts compiled in the book *Empat Episode Perang Padri (Four Padri War Plays)* (2002). They were Tuanku Koto Tuo in *Perguruan (The College)*; Tuanku Nan Renceh in *Perburuan (The Hunt)*; Tuanku Imam Bonjol in *Pengakuan (The Confession)*; and Sultan Abdul Jalil in *Penyeberangan (The Crossing)*.¹⁷ The four characters are four figures originating from the history of the Padri War in West Sumatra, from which the endless dialogue between Islamic *syara'* and Minangkabau customs began. Thus, from the selection of characters who are then processed into characters in the text of his drama, it appears that Wisran Hadi is directly targeting the epicenter of the thought debate that has built the present structure of Minangkabau culture itself, namely a long dynamic and at the same time an endless negotiation between the two value systems. in the culture of the Minangkabau ethnic community.

Although Wisran Hadi presents the four characters as protagonists or central characters who are the center of storytelling in his texts, Wisran Hadi does not place them as protagonists, as tragedy and realism put them. This means, even though at first glance it appears that these characters are similar to Aristotle's tragedy commonly referred to as a 'tragic hero', the way Wisran Hadi tells the characters is not like the 'tragic

¹⁶ Abdullah Taufik, "Studi Tentang Minangkabau," in *Dialektika Minangkabau; Dalam Kemelut Sosial Dan Politik*, ed. A.A. Navis (Padang: Genta Singgalang Press, 1983), 155–69.

¹⁷ Hadi Wisran, *Empat Lakon Perang Paderi* (Bandung: Angkasa, 2002).

rhythm' tell the characters. The reason is that not all events in the text are centered on the thoughts and feelings of the main character or protagonist.

In *Perguruan (The College)*, for example, where Tuanku Koto Tuo is the protagonist, readers and viewers will find a character who, although he looks 'manly' and very human, is filled with love and anger that makes him hesitate to take a stand. towards his students, himself but the plot does not completely flow based on the thoughts and feelings of my Lord Koto Tuo alone. *Perguruan (The College)* also includes comments from the students as well as from other followers of Tuanku Koto Tuo. At first glance, the way that Wisran Hadi presents his comments on Tuanku Koto Tuo through dialogue from the students and followers is similar to the way that Bertholt Brecht hoped to create an Epic character, namely a character who is not dealing with psychological developments or the development of his own destiny, but a character who is dealing alone with history.

The mode of characterization of the main character is also very thick in the script of *Pengakuan (The Confession)* where Tuanku Imam Bonjol, one who was appointed a National Hero of the Republic of Indonesia, becomes the central character or protagonist. In the text, Wisran Hadi even shows that the decisions taken by the character are mostly based on debates and comments from his followers in Bonjol, as well as people who came to ask for his help at Fort Bonjol, instead of showing psychological developments, or the development of the soul in search of answers, as in an Aristotelian tragedy. In *Pengakuan (The Confession)*, Wisran Hadi shows that a historical figure, a hero like Tuanku Imam Bonjol, can be in a situation of hesitation not because he follows what he thinks and feels himself, but because he tries to puts himself as a public figure, where the complaints and pains of the people are the source of the political decisions he takes, which are not always correct.

These two figures, Tuanku Koto Tuo and Tuanku Imam Bonjol, have very different positions in Indonesia's formal history. While Tuanku Imam Bonjol became one of the national heroes of the Republic of Indonesia, and considered as the leader of the Padri War, Tuanku Koto Tuo, who was actually Tuanku Imam Bonjol's teacher, was someone who was rarely talked about if not at all. In this regard, Wisran Hadi expresses his concept, that for him the task of literature is to point out things that are weaknesses in terms of historical writing.

For Wisran Hadi, the figures who later became national heroes in this Republic were those who were actually conquered or captured by the Dutch colonials. Based on that, according to Wisran Hadi, the characterization of several people in history is an indirect form of hegemony from the Dutch colonial to the indigenous Indonesian people. And unfortunately, this method was continued by the newly established

government, the Republic of Indonesia. Therefore, according to Wisran Hadi, that is where the main task of literature is, to show the other side of the history of a nation.¹⁸

Furthermore, Wisran Hadi shows by his characterization in his play, that all historical figures are basically ordinary people. They can be in doubt, and not always have certainty and firmness in deciding various things which are later recorded as history or considered as important moments in history. In *Perguruan (The College)*, Wisran Hadi shows how hesitant Tuanku Koto Tuo, when he has to choose between the hard-line Islam brought by his students, including Tuanku Nan Renceh, and the other side, traditional Islam which tends to be more lenient and accommodating, which He has developed over the years. Tuanku Koto Tuo (in the play referred as GURU) is also hesitant to support his followers taking up arms against people who are considered to be carrying out heresy or customs outside of religious teachings, namely the *adat*, or should instead fight them, because the heretics are their own relatives, while the Padri are the ones to blame for the death of his wife and two children.

GURU:

Which one should we choose? And we definitely won't choose one. Because we cannot combine these two tools. I've always said, stand up for the truth. Straighten up. It should. But don't let the truth be a tool to separate us. What's the truth about fighting for? To destroy life? No, isn't it? If you knew how my heart broke because of my wife and two children being killed, maybe you wouldn't be as hard at pushing me to choose. For others, it may be what causes him to become wild, or vicious, or seek revenge. But for me, it's the wound that matters. I don't hate those of you who uphold the truth, I don't hate those in power. Both are presented to us, for comparison...¹⁹

This technique of characterizing the characters in the text of the play then influences the plot or storyline written by Wisran Hadi in his play scripts. In *Perguruan (The College)*, the story is not bound to a 24-hour period as suggested by the realism convention in theater but takes place over a relatively long period of time, a matter of weeks, months, and even years. Because of that, the technique of staging or the unity of events in

¹⁸ Hadi Wisran, *Anak Dipangku Kemenakan Di BIM: Sagarobak Tulak Buah Tangan*, ed. Darman Moenir (Padang: Lembaga Kebudayaan Ranah, 2013).

¹⁹ Hadi, *Empat Lakon Perang Paderi*, 84.

Wisran Hadi's script cannot be seen as a linear plot but rather a storytelling pattern that resembles an epic, in which events take place in diachronic time and sometimes simultaneously.

What readers and spectators can catch from the story is a 'rhetorical rhythm' in which the debates escalate. There is a debate between the thought of purification of *syara'* brought by those who had just studied in Mecca and brought Wahhabi teachings to Minangkabau, and the traditional view, which wanted to maintain traditional habits through the legitimacy of Minangkabau customs. Likewise, in *Pengakuan (The Confession)*, event after event focuses on one debated idea, should Bonjol give up the peace and prosperity they have achieved to join the war to defend the Padri and defend the *syara'*; or they must maintain peace, prosperity and tranquility in their own country, where *adat* and *syara'* are carried out side by side.

Judging from his play scripts' characterization techniques and plot construction techniques, Wisran Hadi does not seem close to Greek tragedy or realism in the West. A general theme emerges from the play texts, which is about humanity because all the play texts are centered on a complete picture of the characters in history as human beings who are filled with doubt, love, and hatred, which makes it difficult to decide and overwhelmed with anger and feelings of fear of loss and so on. Thus, thematically it can be said that the play script contains about humans and their humanity as the adage often said by Wisran Hadi about the purpose of theater and writing drama, namely "humanizing humans," which means putting humans back in their nature as humans, beings who are always in a liminal situation, always in a situation of conflict and crisis, where they must always choose and their choices are not always right.

In *Perburuan (The Hunt)*, Wisran Hadi presents a loud dialogue, how *syara'* which shakes customs, can become a blanket from greed and lust. In a conversation, Tuanku Koto Tuo (Teacher), who in the play is named as LELAKI II, argues loudly with Tuanku Nan Renceh (Student), who in the play is named PEMUDA I. LELAKI II comes to confirm the news that PEMUDA I has kills his mother's sister, because he thinks she is committing heresy, by continuing the tradition or custom. But then news spread that PEMUDA I married the son of his mother's sister, who, in the view of matrilineal Minangkabau customs, could not be married because they were brothers and sisters. PEMUDA I accused LELAKI II of having been caught in rumors or hoaxes. According to him, what is more important is the purification of *syara'*. On that basis he burned the college of Tuanku Koto Tuo, even though it was the place where he had studied.

However, Wisran Hadi still managed to show in *Perburuan (The Hunt)*, that PEMUDA I (Tuanku Nan Renceh) was still an ordinary human

being. The figure who by the Dutch historian is considered the most fierce and courageous character, is that humans still have doubts in their attitudes, even tend to regret what they have done. PEMUDA I (Tuanku Nan Renceh) clearly saw that his attitude was an attitude that emerged from a blurred view, in meetings, clashes, as well as the struggle between Islamic *syara'* and Minangkabau customs.

PEMUDA I:
Dear Allah...
My teacher, teacher.
My eyes light up because of your knowledge
Calm my mind in your faith
But in the confluence of two circles
Between religion and customs
Between belief and trust
Thousands of bats marched to the South
Blackened vision and life...²⁰

Wisran Hadi presents Tuanku Imam Bonjol in the third play, *Pengakuan (The Confession)*. The play was filled with debate between two parties, the *adat* party, and the *padri* party. At the end of the story, Tuanku Imam Bonjol, the hero in the version of national history, which departs from colonial records, is manifested by Wisran Hadi as a tragic hero, the defeated, unable to withstand the burden of the division of his people, where the *adat* party and the *padri* party continue to fight. He, refuses to be called by the name “*Imam*,” (leader) because he feels like a failure. At the end of the play, Wisran Hadi describes Tuanku Imam Bonjol (who in the text is called TOKOH I) leaving his people, which of course is easy to relate to the incident of the capture of Tuanku Imam Bonjol by the Dutch Colonial in history. A figure who in history is called a hero, was embodied by Wisran Hadi as an ordinary human being, who also has limits. A boundary that arises from the fight, which always asks him to choose between *syara'* and *adat*.

TOKOH I:
Don't call me by that big name, while I can't prevent the
division between us. Gentlemen, building and maintaining
Bonjol is not difficult. But maintaining unity, I was hurt by it.

...

²⁰ Hadi, *Empat Lakon Perang Paderi.*, 152.

That big name has magnified my failure. Peto Syarif, my name is, just call it. Hmm...! Imam Bonjol. The man who failed across the equator.²¹

The dialogue between Minangkabau customs and Islam as a source of searching for the meaning of life appears more clearly in the last play text, namely *Penyeberangan (The Crossing)*, where Sultan Abdul Jalil is the protagonist. In the play, Wisran Hadi creates two characters who are brothers, but stand on opposite sides. DEMANG, who is supposed to be the personification of Sutan Alam Bagagarsyah, the last king of Pagaruyung, is a representative of the traditional figure, who holds such a great grudge against the *Padri*, because of what *Padri* has done to the royal family, his people.

DEMANG:

Yes. The recent war has separated us and left us with choices. Since our *Rumah Gadang* was burned by the *Padri*, my grudge has never been extinguished. In various ways I tried to get revenge. Mr. Commander appointed me Demang, I accepted. Bearing the title *Sutan* which should be an heirloom title for you at the urging of the Commander, I also accept it. I was swept away by a grudge and no one caught up with me or freed me from the rising tide. And *Wan* himself, my brother, never rebuked me. As if holding a grudge against me because of the heirloom title that I took away. Since then we crossed paths.²²

While on the other hand, there is IMAM (Sultan Abdul Jalil), who tries to find a middle way, between the choice of supporting the *padri* with purification of *syara'* or defending his people, which means the royal family and their *adat*. IMAM, in his hesitation chose the third path, which means not choosing both. He left both sides, isolated himself, tried to build a new civilization, which reconciled *adat* and *syara'*. A choice that at that time might have been wise, but it would become the source of the 'eternal paradox' of the Minangkabau ethnic community in West Sumatra.

IMAM:

Religion is more reassuring to my soul, *Yung*. If *Padri* burns our house, it's not religion to me that burns it. But people who take cover behind religious struggles to vent the jealousy of history on us. I don't side with them, but I have to

²¹ Hadi, *Empat Lakon Perang Paderi*, 251

²² Hadi, *Empat Lakon Perang Paderi*, 319

defend my religion. Should! Without religion this country will be swept away by Batang Karan river to estuary, to the sea, until we are no longer in the record of this life.²³

While in these four plays Wisran Hadi criticizes the 'eternal paradox' through the *padri* figures, which means from the *syara*' side, He also criticizes Minangkabau *adat* in a fairly harsh way, in the form of plays that depart from oral historical stories about the establishment of Minangkabau customs as a source of value systems. This can be seen in at least two plays in a collection of play texts entitled *Empat Sandiwara Orang Melayu (Four Plays of the Malays)* (2020), in the play entitled *Dara Jingga* and *Cinduo Mato*. In *Dara Jingga*, Wisran Hadi raised one of the stories that historically referred to as the impact of the Pamalayu Expedition, by presenting two figures who are seen as the founders of Minangkabau customs, namely Datuak Perpatiah (in the play PERPATIH) and Datuak Katumanggungan (in the play TUMANGGUNG).

TUMANGGUNG:

In the end, things got messy and upside down! Religion, ordinances, customs, even history will be shaken.

PERPATIH:

It is precisely by overturning something that we find everything. The obscured and the obscured can be easily distinguished.

TUMANGGUNG:

The truth that is found is also the overturned truth.

PERPATIH :

The true truth, everyone understands.²⁴

Meanwhile, in *Cinduo Mato*, which depicts one of the greatest epics in the oral tradition of the Minangkabau people, Wisran Hadi presents unexpected intrigues behind the founding of the Pagaruyung kingdom, which is believed to be a symbol of Minangkabau customs. The figures that are glorified in mythology are embodied by Wisran Hadi as characters full of cunning, hatred and at the same time doubts and fears.

²³ Hadi, *Empat Lakon Perang Paderi*, 319

²⁴ Hadi Wisran, *Empat Sandiwara Orang Melayu* (Bandung: Angkasa, 2000), 130.

CINDUO MATO:

No one has been able to name this baby. And no one he would call father! Oh, Puti Bungsu. You sent this innocent baby without your love for him. Are you willing to part with your own child rather than you being separated from my brother Dang Tuanku.

...
Why are you running away with a king who is afraid to die! A king who dares not look at today's reality! Youngest Puti. Give affection, love and surrender to your child, not for a man who is afraid to see his reality.²⁵

Similar to the four characters in the Padri war, the characters in *Dara Jingga* and *Cinduo Mato*, are characters from the *kaba* and oral history are presented as humans, not flawless heroes. They hesitate in choosing, take a stance in the dark, and are therefore tragic, because the choice is irreversible, as are the consequences. One of the implicit consequences, is that in the development of customs, religion, and even the history of the Minangkabau ethnicity itself is equally shaky, and as a result always have a fear of seeing oneself in the face of today's reality.

Wisran Hadi's Dramaturgy: The Eternal Paradox as Aesthetics Source

However, it would be a bit too hasty, if we conclude that Wisran Hadi's style of drama, which is seen from the way he builds characters, constructs the plot, and the themes he chooses is close to the way of storytelling or style of Bertolt Brecht's epic theater. Because this kind of storytelling is embedded in the oral literature of the Minangkabau community itself, called *kaba*. The way of telling stories from the *kaba* also seems to be centered on a character, so usually, the stories are titled with the name of the character, but tell other things outside the character itself, also tell other characters in detail and proportional. So characters who seem to be the center of the story are often just a way to trigger a story where other characters are also brought up with their thoughts and feelings.

Of course, this also affects the plot of *kaba*, which, like an epic, the story moves from place to time so easily. A *kaba* narrator is very good at transferring the events in his story to a different time and place as if to say that what they are conveying is mere *kaba*, is a game. So that the main impression of the *kaba*, is a game of logic or just a tool to convey something much bigger than the *kaba* itself, namely lessons about life, and lessons about being human. That lesson, according to Umar Junus, was

²⁵ Hadi, *Empat Sandiwara Orang Melayu.*, 314.

obtained through the *kaba* because of criticism of the Minangkabau social system itself.²⁶

This understanding is important to explore Wisran Hadi's drama in terms of play genre, namely the main effect it has on the audience. Wisman Hadi's dramas do not aim to create a sense of 'fear and pity' like tragedy or cure 'anger and envy' like comedy. Wisran Hadi's plays are more accurately seen as a parody, a way of creating critical power for the audience, by comparing two texts that look similar, but are also different at the same time, whereas the second text, the play, is a form of ridicule and scorn for the first text, whether it be an oral tradition or even historical text.²⁷

Some authors have indicated this parody in the works of Wisran Hadi,²⁸ but it is still missed to see that parody is an important strategy in postcolonial drama, which aims to raise awareness about the history, as well as dismantle colonial hegemony and its legacies.²⁹ Furthermore, by developing parody as his drama genre, Wisran Hadi presents a juxtaposition to the audience and readers, which is closely related to the fact that throughout its history, researchers have seen Minangkabau society live in various dichotomies and 'eternal paradoxes'. Not only between *syara*' and *adat*, but also between modernism and traditionalism.

But in that way, Wisran Hadi recommends an aesthetic concept, namely "Aesthetics that comes from Truth." Both Islamic teachings, as well as Minangkabau culture, are always looking for sources of philosophy of beauty by various thinkers. However, Wisran Hadi shows well that the beauty in *syara*' is the beauty of the *akliah* (mind), displayed by works of art that can stimulate the mind and reflection to seek the truth. Meanwhile, in terms of customs, Wisran Hadi shows the importance of language for the Minangkabau community, which comes from a philosophical value described in the Minangkabau adage, "*Nan kuriak kundi, nan merah sago. Nan baiak budi, nan endah bahaso.*" (the striated ones are seeds, the red ones are saga, the good ones are wisdom, the

²⁶ Umar Junus, *Kaba Dan Sistem Sosial Minangkabau: Suatu Problema Sosiologi Sastra* (Jakarta: Balai Pustaka, 1984).

²⁷ Linda Hutcheon, *A Theory of Parody* (New York: Methuen, Inc., 1985).

²⁸ Rusyda Ulva, "Dara Jingga, Wisran Hadi: Parodi Terhadap Kekuasaan (Dara Jingga, Wisran Hadi: A Power Parody)," *Salingka: Majalah Ilmiah Bahasa Dan Sastra* 12, no. 1 (2015): 51–63, <https://doi.org/10.26499/salingka.v12i01.33>; Syafril, "Idiom-Idiom Estetik Pastiche, Parodi, Kitsch, Camp, Dan Skizofrenia Dalam Karya Teater Postmodern Indonesia Jalan Lurus (Aesthetic Idioms of Pastiche, Parody, Kitsch, Camp, and Schizophrenia in Indonesian Postmodern Theater Works, Jalan Lurus)," *Komposisi: Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa, Sastra, Dan Seni* 9, no. 2 (2008): 132–42, <https://doi.org/10.24036/komposisi.v9i2.97>.

²⁹ Helen Gilbert and Joanne Tomkins, *Postcolonial Drama: Theory, Practice, Politics* (New York: Routledge, 2006).

beautiful ones are language). Through his scripts, Wisran shows that adage is not just an abstract concept, but can be operated in practice.³⁰

For Wisran Hadi Himself, Islam and Minangkabau customs are something that must be addressed differently. Regarding Minangkabau customs, Wisran Hadi recommends the use of *raso* (filling) rather than *pareso* (thinking) in addressing and interpreting customs. He invites people to temporarily leave rationality, which is learned from Western philosophy, and replace it with 'love.'³¹ As for Islamic *syara'*, Wisran sees it as a guide for *akhlaq* (morality), in terms of living life as a human being, and in becoming a human being.³²

Keindahan bahasa dan pencarian akan kebenaran itulah yang oleh Wisran Hadi diwujudkan dalam permainan kata dan dalam pertunjukan berubah menjadi permainan benda-benda. Sesuatu yang bersumber dari penggaliannya atas *randai*, teater tradisional masyarakat Minangkabau yang memiliki fungsi pendidikan simbolis dalam mempersiapkan orang-orang muda Minangkabau pergi merantau. Fungsi tersebut ditunjukkan oleh *silek* dan *mancak* (seni bela diri lokal) yang merupakan prototipe *randai*, dan *buah kato* (kata-kata). Permainan *randai* adalah wahana untuk berlatih mempertahankan diri, baik dengan tubuh maupun kata-kata. Di dalamnya ada pendidikan karakter dalam bentuk aforisme tentang paradoks abadi, yakni mempraktikkan Islam dengan baik, dan memenuhi kewajiban filial, terutama pada ibu, sebagai bagian dari matrilineal Minangkabau. Justru dengan cara ini, *randai* dan merantau secara tradisional saling memperkuat tempat masing-masing dalam masyarakat Minangkabau.

The beauty of language and the search for truth is what Wisran Hadi embodies in word games and performance, it turns into a game of objects. Something that stems from his excavations of the *randai*, the traditional theater of the Minangkabau community for preparing young people to *merantau* (wander). This function is demonstrated by *silek* (local martial arts) which are the prototypes of *randai*, and *kato* (words). *Randai* is a vehicle for practicing self-defense, both with body and words. In it, there is character education in the form of aphorisms about the eternal paradox, namely practicing Islam well, and fulfilling filial obligations, especially to mothers, as part of the Minangkabau matrilineal. Precisely in this way,

³⁰ Dede Pramayoza, *Melukis Di Atas Pentas: Selisik Penyutradaraan Teater Wisran Hadi* (Yogyakarta: Penerbit Deepublish, 2020), 218.

³¹ Hadi, *Anak Dipangku Kemenakan Di BIM: Sagarobak Tulak Buah Tangan..*, 11.

³² Hadi, *Anak Dipangku Kemenakan Di BIM: Sagarobak Tulak Buah Tangan..*,

randai and *merantau* traditionally reinforce each other's place in Minangkabau society³³

By floating the eternal paradox as an aesthetic source, Wisran Hadi writes historical figures as a new form of historicization, which is also a form of 'resistance' against the authoritarian rule of the New Order-Soeharto in Indonesia, which indirectly is a way of opening the faucets of democracy.³⁴ With an aesthetic that stems from that timeless paradox, Wisran Hadi's involvement in the Indonesian theater scene is part of the decentralization movement, a way to fight the patriarchal power (especially synonymous with Javanese culture) that is ruling the country under Suharto's leadership, which in many ways resembles with Dutch colonialism.³⁵

In short, the aesthetic of the eternal paradox in Wisran Hadi's dramaturgy shows the uniqueness of Minangkabau society, where conflicts of thought are not only recognized but institutionalized within the social system itself. The eternal paradox aesthetic automatically affirms the fact that for the Minangkabau community, conflict is seen dialectically, as essential to achieving community integration.³⁶ Nowadays, the aesthetic of the eternal paradox needs to be offered more and more, as the conflict of ideas about Minangkabau local culture intensifies. This is because various traditions which of course become the main capital, are once again faced with those who want to purify the implementation of *syara'*, who tend to view various cultural or customary practices as a practice filled with *bid'ah* (not by religious teachings). Those with different opinions can learn from Wisran Hadi's eternal paradox aesthetic, where diametrical differences become a 'dramaturgical material', a treasure trove of ideas that became the source of the creation of his plays.

Conclusion

Instead of seeing the antagonistic difference between Islamic *syara'* values and Minangkabau *adat* values as a destructive force, Wisran Hadi instead shows in his drama texts that these two value systems are a major force in the search for meaning. The dialogue between the two is a source of wisdom and a source of ideas for progress for the Minangkabau community. Moreover, Wisran Hadi also points out that basically, it is through the endless dialogue between these two value systems that

³³ Craig Latrell, "Widening the Circle: The Refiguring of West Sumatran Randai," *Asian Theatre Journal* 16, no. 2 (1999): 248–59.

³⁴ Michael H Bodden, *Resistance on the National Stage: Modern Theatre and Politics in Late New Order Indonesia* (Athens: Ohio University Press, 2010), 18.

³⁵ Evan Darwin Winet, *Indonesian Postcolonial Theatre: Spectral Genealogies and Absent Faces* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2010), 92.

³⁶ Abdullah, "Studi Tentang Minangkabau."

Minangkabau society will continually learn to adapt to the various advances presented by modernity, a postcolonial reality that will constantly have to be thought, explored, and examined by the Minangkabau community. In addition to adaptability, the dialogue between these two value systems is a trigger for the ability of appropriation, to absorb and then accept the various advances and sophistication offered by modernity, to adapt them to the daily realities of the Minangkabau people.

Based on all that, it can be seen that the experience of beauty that is offered in the dramas written by Wisran Hadi to the readers and the audience is an endless dialogical experience. An experience where they can see that the clashes, differences, and even struggles between the values of Islamic *syara'* and Minangkabau *adat*, which they live and feel every day, are one of the most valuable sources in their efforts to continuously renew their way of life or live, their *weltanschauung*. Throughout the drama scripts, he writes and throughout the theatrical performances he directs, Wisran Hadi encourages readers and audiences to always be in a situation as a subject who must constantly judge, not only good or bad but also appropriate and incompatible with various views that are born from the meeting. at the same time the struggle and negotiation between the two value systems, Islamic *syara'* on the one hand and Minangkabau *adat* on the other.

And because this dialogue will always exist in the life of the Minangkabau people in West Sumatra, as a dialogue that will never end, it can be said that Wisran Hadi through his drama scripts and performances, offers the audience a form of dramaturgy with the aim of the primary experience of the eternal paradox. An experience that presents a juxtaposition between two value systems that tend to be contradictory. Based on its epistemology, this form of dramaturgy can be called the Eternal Paradox Aesthetic. This aesthetic experience emerges from an endless paradox between two value systems, Islamic *syara'* and Minangkabau *adat*, which has brought the Minangkabau community in West Sumatra to the reality of their present.

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